

Sister Nivedita and Sri Aurobindo: A Cherished Relation of Unwavering Love

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Abstract:

Sister Nivedita and Sri Aurobindo had been the twin pillars of Indian Nationalism. Sister Nivedita has been the epitome of love, sacrifice, dedication and Indianness. On the other hand, Sri Aurobindo stands out as the great Indian idealist who had been the inspiration of the youths in ushering revolutionary activities, mesmerizing the nation with his oratory skills, bridging politics and spirituality and later emerging as the great spiritual leader of the country. The Duo shared a common identity inspite of being stalwarts in their respective arena. They both earnestly loved the motherland and devoutly craved and fought for its political and spiritual salvation. The paper unfurls the different dimensions in their relations and endeavours to unfold the commonness and dissimilarities between them. They mutually have complemented and supplemented themselves in India's struggle for independence.

Key words:

Nivedita, Aurobindo, Revolution, politics, reverence, freedom, Government, Ramakrishna, Vivekananda.

Introduction:

Among the foreigners who had dedicated themselves for India, Sister Nivedita stands out as an unique example of selfless love and sacrifice for our motherland. Margaret Elizabeth Noble as she was called was impressed by Swami Vivekananda's words on India. She had firmly believed that she belonged to India and her salvation rested on India's emancipation from foreign domination. She had travelled through the length and breadth of the country. Her deep historical sense had given her the insight to carry out the task of India's liberation. As 'Nivedita', she had dedicated her heart and soul for India's freedom. She disassociated herself from the Ramakrishna Mission so that her political involvement in no way should invite the wrath of the British Government on the Mission. It was openly declared in the leading newspapers of Calcutta that henceforth her work and deeds were independent and in no way associated with Belur Math or the Mission.

She had become an inspiration to all. Her realization that India's progress was dependent on the nation's independence had made her actively involved in political work along with her commitment for the socio- religious causes. She appealed to the youths of India to work selflessly for the cause of their country along the ideals of Swami Vivekananda. Many young and veteran nationalists of the time were her compatriots and ardent followers. She had thus

stated, “The Indianising of India, the organizing of our national thought, the laying out of our line of March, all this is to be done by us, not by others on our behalf. We ordain ourselves intellectually free” (Sister Nivedita, 1967). Sri Aurobindo had remarked that India cannot be too grateful to her for what she did for our country.

Sri Aurobindo:

Like Sister Nivedita, Sri Aurobindo had also been inspired by Swami Vivekananda. This had been the common factor that enabled the two great figures of Indian nationalism come closer and fight for India’s freedom. Sri Aurobindo’s wide reading in England had familiarized him with the weakness of the western culture. He had followed the Irish liberation movement. He had vehemently criticized the methods of the Indian National Congress in *Induprakash*. He was mesmerized by Bankim Chandra Chatterjee’s revolutionary novel *Anandamath*. He spent the first few years in Baroda and engaged himself in reading, writing, meeting political activists and closely watching the political situation. His words and works reflected his earnest urge to set the motherland free. He was convinced that the demonstration of strength was the only way to drive the British away from India. He was stirred by the ideal of selfless sacrifice as propagated by the Ramakrishna Mission. He had stated that what India looked-for at the hour was not western science and Industrialization but “strength physical, strength mental, strength moral and above all strength spiritual which is the one inexhaustible and imperishable source of all others. In the absence of strength we are like men in a dream who have hands but cannot seize or strike, who have feet but cannot run (Nandakumar, 2017). The Motherland, according to Aurobindo, was’ neither a piece of earth, nor a figure of speech, nor a fiction of the mind. The Motherland is a mighty Shakti, composed of the Shaktis of all the millions of units that make up the nation’. Only selfless sacrifice and renunciation would unite the Indians. He had written to his wife, Mrinalini Devi that while the others looked towards the motherland as an inert piece of matter comprising of a few meadows and forests, fields, hills and rivers, he looked at her as the Mother.

Aurobindo never liked the timid constitutional agitation of the Congress. He wished to propagate secret revolution and create strong organization which would try to prepare the nation for armed insurrection against the British rule. He also desired to promulgate public propaganda so as to inspire the whole nation to the idea of freedom (Pravrajika, 1961). When Aurobindo joined politics, the idea of liberty appeared as an illusion to most Indians. Aurobindo favoured the practice of swadeshi and passive resistance by the mass so as to weaken the ties of foreign authority (Pravrajika, 1963). He had sent Jyotindramohan Banerjee to Calcutta to establish secret society in Bengal. Aurobindo himself came to Calcutta for the establishment of secret society. He wished to gather the youths and spread revolutionary ideas among them. The youths should carry out horse rides, exercises, boxing to enhance their strength. He waged revolutionary war against the British through ‘*Yugantor*’ newspaper (Sri Aurobindo, 1972).

Almost all the great leaders of the time perceived the glowing spiritual fire and dynamism of his personality and hailed him with one voice “ as the brightest star in the political ferment of India and the voice incarnate, free, of India’s soul.” His politics was not of the western type. He followed the Indian tradition in which politics was considered as part of Dharma. His principle and vision were to revive the Indian tradition and his dream was to apply the ancient ideal of the Sanatana Dharma as it had never been applied before to the problem of politics and the work of national revival.

Methodology

A research methodology describes the techniques and procedures used to identify and analyze information regarding a research topic. In writing this paper, primary and secondary research procedures have been used. Sister Nivedita’s works have been compiled as Complete Works of Sister Nivedita and published by Advaita Ashrama in 5 volumes. She has written several letters to her near and dear ones which are collected as Letters of Sister Nivedita in 2 volumes. Her notes, letters, diaries shed light on Nivedita’s views about India.. She had intimate links with great contemporaries of her time like Rabindranath Tagore, Sir Jagadish Chandra Bose and Mrs. Abala Bose, Gopal Krishna Gokhale, Surendra Nath Banerjee, Abanindranath Tagore, Aurobindo Ghosh and many more. Nivedita’s correspondence with these luminaries and their writings about the Sister are all primary sources for a study about Sister Nivedita. Aurobindo Ghose had spoken about himself in his books. Renowned educationists, academicians, journalists and authors have contributed enriched articles on Sister Nivedita and Sri Aurobindo’s philosophy and their contributions in social regeneration, national awakening and so on. These constitute the secondary sources for jotting down this article. I have attempted to go through these textual sources, both primary and secondary, learn the different standpoint of the authors about Nivedita and Aurobindo and how Nivedita had been a guide and true companion of the latter.

Discussion:

Sister Nivedita and Revolutionary activities:

After the passing away of Swamiji on 4th July 1902, Nivedita did not spare much time in mourning for her Guru but like a true disciple undertook the task of building a strong India. Nivedita went around delivering lectures on Swami Vivekananda and his works. Her fiery words and in depth knowledge on Indian culture had aroused the youths. Swamiji had dreamt of free India and had hoped that Sister Nivedita would ignite the national desire of the Indians. Her writing skills, her oratory capacity, her profound respect towards Indian culture and her readiness to sacrifice were sufficient reasons for rejuvenating the people of the land. She had spoken of the unity among the Indians. She had thus stated:

“ the task before us is to educate ourselves in the consciousness of our own unity. Perfect harmony and mental cohesion of the body politic is the necessary antecedent of political mastery which is another name for that relative good which we call national freedom” (Sister Nivedita, 1968). Her definition of nation was meant to arouse interest in the shared past of an enslaved nation, in their artistic heritage, in the scientific achievements and in the diversity of

its religious traditions and cultures (Som, 2017). She visited different parts of the country and relentlessly delivered lectures on Swamiji's ideals, Indian Women, Asian life, Hindu mind on Indian Science and so on. There was a great similarity between the speeches of Swami Vivekananda and Sister Nivedita. Nivedita's words were reflections of Swamiji's thoughts on the upliftment of the common man and aspiration for liberty. She had given heart touching speeches on nationalism, need for practicing Brahmacharya, and conservation of religion that echoed her profound knowledge about Indian life, her liberal attitude and unquestioned reverence for India. She had always endeavoured to spread the ideals and messages of Ramakrishna- Vivekananda.

After the Partition of Bengal, Sister Nivedita also actively participated in non-cooperation and passive resistance. She had relentlessly tried to unveil the true character of British rule, encourage the people to be free, appealed to them not to imitate the west but respect one's own culture, rituals, education and become true Indians. Her actions were not influenced by Aurobindo. Aurobindo was aware of the existence of many societies. He tried to unite them under a single organization with barrister P. Mitra as the leader of the revolution in Bengal and a Central Council of five persons in which Nivedita was one of the members. She had given her books on the history of the Irish revolt, the history of American war of Independence, the history of the Dutch republic, the life of Mazzini and Garibaldi in the Italian unification, the economic books of Dadabhai Naoroji and Romesh Chandra Dutt to the young revolutionaries. According to Lizelle Reymond, her house had been the shelter of the revolutionaries where they received food, money and road map for escape. This suggests her connection with the revolutionary societies. She had extended her support in preparing the youths for armed revolution. However she probably had no role in the running of these organizations. She knew that it was almost impossible to openly fight with the British Raj. Therefore, recourse to secret movement would not be unfair or unjust. She was in favour of setting up societies both in the villages and towns so as to prepare the nation for armed resistance. She was in no way associated with revolutionary terrorism. Girija Shankar Roychoudhury however commented that before she met Swamiji in 1895 in London, she had been in close touch with Kropatkin whose teachings had turned her into a revolutionary. She had actively participated in Irish Home Rule Movement. Raymond further had pointed out that she was also involved in the experiment of making bombs that the revolutionaries tried at the secret shelter at Muraripukur. Nivedita would arrange for the experiments in the laboratory of the Presidency College. As Jagadish Chandra Bose was a close friend of Nivedita, it was not difficult for her to send one or two young revolutionaries in the laboratory of the Presidency College.

The active role of Nivedita had not been mentioned in the writings of the revolutionaries. It had been only stated that she was sympathetic towards the revolutionary actions and had bestowed different books to them. Her close associates like Rabindranath Tagore, Abanindranath Tagore, Sir Jadunath Sarkar, S.K.Ratcliffe and Professor Patrick Geddes etc had never mentioned her as a revolutionary or that she had led the revolutionary movements. They unanimously had opined that Nivedita had accepted India as her homeland and had dedicated herself for her. She simultaneously took interest in the different ideologies

professed by the leaders of the Indian Community (Pravrajika, 1961.) Her supreme desire was to see a strong and powerful India.

Sister Nivedita and Sri Aurobindo:

Both Aurobindo and Sister Nivedita were active in revolutionary nationalism. This association was strictly political. By the time Sister Nivedita and Sri Aurobindo met at Baroda, they had known one another through their writings, and their flaming desire for India's freedom brought them closer. Aurobindo was greatly inspired by Nivedita's *Kali, the Mother*. Nivedita thought him as the nationalist leader whose sweltering articles in the *Indu Prakash*, one of Bombay's largest newspapers had impressed her about Aurobindo's innate qualities and huge capacity in awakening the nation. She admired the way Sri Aurobindo was training the youths for revolutionary action when the call would come for unshackling the Mother. Both were dedicated soldiers to India's cause. As Lizelle Raymond had stated that when Sister Nivedita met Aurobindo at Baroda, she had requested him to come to Calcutta but Aurobindo replied that he would come later (Reymond, 1953). Nivedita told him that he could rely upon her as his ally.

Nivedita knew well the techniques of secret movement. So, she had not spoken about Aurobindo in her works and letters. However in those letters that would not come under the vigilance of the Government, she had uttered Aurobindo's name, rather his pseudo name as "A. G", Recalcitrant leader, "Bengali Mazzini", "leader of the Nationalists" and so on.

They mutually respected each other because both were extremely talented, educated, great writers, believed in the path of renunciation and selflessness and shared revolutionary outlook. She considered him as the best among the writers who wrote in English at that time. Both Jagadish Chandra Bose and Aurobindo visited her house at Bosepara lane and Nivedita gave Swami Vivekananda's *Rajyoga* to Aurobindo when she first met him at Baroda. Although their relation was seen in political matters, they had profound respect for Ramakrishna and Vivekananda. They were the inspiration behind the nationalist movement. She had always been anxious about this revolutionary leader. She felt that the movement would continue as long as he was behind the bars.

She arrived at Baroda where she was requested to speak on the Asian Unity and the Shakti Worship. The King and the Queen of Baroda had invited her in a tea party. Here she met Aurobindo for the first time. Sri Aurobindo and Khashi Rao went to the station to welcome Nivedita. She criticized the ugliness of the College building and its top heavy dome and praised the small houses of the householders on the way that impressed Aurobindo. She had requested the Maharaja of Baroda, Swoyaji Rao to assist the revolutionaries but he had not committed to do so.

Nivedita had avowed that her aim was nation –making. She eagerly worked to free the county from the fetters of dependence. She could not accept the foreign authority and the corruptions associated with it and thereby prayed for its freeing. She delivered blazing words to stir the youths with nationalism. She often visited the Anushilan Samiti. On January, 1903, after returning to Calcutta, she joined the secret revolutionary society created by Aurobindo. Within a very short time after the meeting at Baroda, Sri Aurobindo moved to Calcutta. He settled down in Calcutta and took charge of *Bande Mataram* that made Sister happy. Although they met a number of times but nothing significant is known about the interactions. Both of them worked tirelessly in educating the Indians on subjects like national education, swadeshi and boycott and the need for inculcating the feeling of national pride. Nivedita uttered, ‘ ‘ O Nationality, come thou to me as joy or sorrow, as honour or shame. Make me thine own.’ ’(Sister Nivedita, 1968).

A lot of stories had been fabricated regarding the relation between Sister Nivedita and Aurobindo Ghose and it has been attempted to prove that she was the leader of revolution. How far she was related to him and how much she had helped Aurobindo could not be established except on assumption. One has to depend on Sri Aurobindo’s account, Nivedita’s writings, the descriptions from other books and works of Nivedita’s contemporaries to arrive at a conclusion on Nivedita’s revolutionary activities. She herself had not mentioned about Aurobindo in her letters and diaries. Sri Aurobindo in a book entitled ‘Sri Aurobindo on Himself’ had opined that his collaboration with her was solely in the secret revolutionary field. She had full support towards Aurobindo’s actions in liberating the motherland.

According to Roychoudhury, a new chapter was initiated in Bengal’s history when the two great revolutionaries met in Baroda for the first time. Two days were important in Nivedita’s life— November, 1895 when she met Vivekananda in London and October, 1902 when she met Aurobindo at Baroda. Aurobindo believed that initially there would be passive resistance which would change to active resistance and become offensive if atrocities were continued by the Government. The movement would change to armed struggle. However it must be remembered that Aurobindo and his associates did not have the full experience of the revolutionary movements like Nivedita. She had gathered the know-how of the revolutionary movement when she was attached to the Irish revolutionary societies in Ireland. Aurobindo firmly believed that the Mother would protect the revolutionaries from all kinds of danger and bless them in secret killing and dacoities. He had supported religion as the source of inspiration behind revolutionary activities. On the other hand, Nivedita did not take recourse to religion or mysticism in her technique. Unlike Aurobindo who composed a poem on *Ma Bhawani*, she did not compose any poem. This difference emanated from their character. But before leaving for the west in 1907, she had met Aurobindo and had stated to him that he was a flaming pioneer of the revolution; the light should never be put off. She concluded with the words ‘ ‘ *Oha Guru ki fateh* ’ ’ (Sengupta,2014).

The programmes as devised by Aurobindo for the revolutionary societies changed over time. Nivedita was against secret dacoities and murder. Her link with Aurobindo was for a very short time. He became the Principal of the National Council and started to reside in Calcutta from 1906. Nivedita left for the west in August, 1907 after she was attacked by malaria in

September, 1906. She returned to India in July, 1909. She was in contact with Aurobindo till he had left for Chandannagar in February, 1910 and she had assisted him in publishing the *Karmayogin* newspaper. Her relation with Aurobindo became closer after her return from the west and this had been acknowledged by Sri Aurobindo .

Alipore Bomb Case or the Muraripukur Conspiracy of 1908.

In 1908, Khudiram Bose and Prafulla Chaki were instructed to kill Mr. Kingsford at Muzaffarpore. The instruction was given by Aurobindo, Raja Subodh Mallick and Charuchandra Dutta from the garden house at Muraripukur. The bomb was thrown on the night of 30th April but unfortunately Mrs. Kennedy and Miss Kennedy were assassinated. After receiving the message through telegram on 1st May in Calcutta, Aurobindo had remarked that the failure was due to darkness. Khudiram Bose was hanged to death and Prafulla Chaki committed suicide. Girija Shankar Roychoudhury blamed Aurobindo and his brother Barindra Ghose for this failure. In the absence of Nivedita, Aurobindo's dependence on unnatural and mystic forces and his brother's over smartness resulted in the loss of such precious lives.

On 2nd May, 1908, Aurobindo, his brother Barindra and 47 others were arrested from Muraripukur garden house and Aurobindo spent one year in prison. On 6th May, 1909, he was acquitted from prison due to the efforts of Chittaranjan Das who questioned in Aurobindo's favour. Barindra's punishment of hanging was changed to exile. Nivedita was well aware of the Alipore bomb case. According to Shankari Prasad Bose, Nivedita had written several articles on 'Modern Review' edited by Ramananda Chattopadhyay. Some of the notes were on political assassination and western sentiment, the genesis of terrorism in Bengal, how to dare and die, the problem of Path and political assassination by bomb throwing etc. (Basu ,1988). Nivedita had remarked that the ultimate cause of terrorism in Bengal must be sought in the utterly selfish, high handed and tyrannical policy of the Government and in the contemptuous and insulting manner in which most official and non-official Anglo Indians have spoken of and treated Bengalis (Sengupta, 2014).

Aurobindo's activities after release from Prison

Aurobindo was released three months before Nivedita reached India in 1909. He underwent spiritual transformation in the detention center. He uttered that Lord Krishna had explained to him the essence of the Gita in the confinement. He was profoundly influenced by Ramakrishna and Vivekananda . He had written in the first issue of *Karmayogin* that Ramakrishna and Vivekananda gave more perfect synthesis than Shankaracharya. Initially he had considered nationalism as the religion but after the spiritual change, he considered Sanatana Dharma or Hinduism as nationalism. After his release, he found that nobody uttered Bandemataram in the atmosphere of terror. He felt himself alone and helpless. The position of the revolutionary societies was at stake on account of oppression by the British Government. This was due to the political situation of the time (excessive repression of the British Government, failure of the revolutionary movement in Bengal, arrest of many

revolutionaries and national leaders). After the murder of Curzon Wyllyne on 1st July, 1909 by Madanlal Dhingra in London, a rumour spread that Aurobindo would be arrested. The rumour of his arrest spread thrice in this manner. Nivedita also had the information of the Government planning to banish Aurobindo. On 30th July, 1909, she had written to Mr & Mrs Ratcliffe that the Government was planning to deport the Bengal Mazzini. In such a situation Nivedita returned to India. The murder of Curzon Wyllyne had created consternation in India and Europe. Aurobindo's intimacy with Nivedita enhanced further after his release. After her arrival, Aurobindo shunned Bankim Chandra's influence and adhered to Shri Krishna and Vivekananda. Aurobindo's mode of operation changed. He started two weekly papers, the *Karmayogin* in English in June and *Dharma* in Bengali in August. He discussed about the influence of Ramakrishna- Vivekananda, Hinduism, and the present political scenario of the country and criticized the Government policies. He clearly mentioned that he was not a part of terrorist groups and his aim was peaceful revolution. He had realized that revolutionary terrorism was not worthy for achieving freedom. He questioned in favour of greater national movement. Another addition was Yoga and Hindu religion. Invigorated with these new ideas, he delivered many public lectures from May to December in 1909. He called upon the Indians to participate in the nationalist movement with determination. His slogan was no compromise and no cooperation without control. Nivedita did not support this action. She had written to S.K.Ratcliffe, the editor of the *Statesman* paper that Aurobindo was not acting judiciously. He believed himself divinely impelled and therefore not to be arrested. "People do strange things for reasons they themselves know. Religious experience and strategy was by no means the same thing and ought not to be confused" (Sengupta, 2014)). The British Government considered Aurobindo as a threat who was trying to revive the movement in Bengal and therefore must be deported. The Detective Department had close vigilance upon him. In this situation, Nivedita apprehended that the British repression could descend down any moment. She wanted Aurobindo to "go into secrecy or to leave British India and act from outside so as to avoid interruption of his work" (Pravrajika, 1963)). But Aurobindo refused to do so as he thought that it was not necessary to accept her suggestion. He would write an open letter in *Karmayogin* which would prevent Government from arresting him.

Aurobindo's Open Letters:

Aurobindo published an 'Open Letter' on 30st July, 1909 in *Karmayogin* after he came to know about the exile plan of the Government regarding him. In the letter, he clearly stated his objectives i.e. passive resistance, non-cooperation, political and economic boycott and establishment of organizations in different provinces. He affirmed "rumour that Calcutta police submitted case for my deportation to the Govt.... In case of my deportation and if I do not return from it, it may stand as my last political will and testament to my countrymen." (Sengupta, 2014).

In the open letter of 30th July, he mentioned that he had no connections with terrorist activities. He wrote, "Our ideal of Swaraj involves no hatred to any other nation nor of the administration which is now established by law in this country—our methods are to evolve a Government of our own for our internal affairs" (Sengupta, 2014). Nivedita suspected that this open letter would fail to convince the Government and prove Aurobindo innocent. The

rulers would attempt to extradite him. The reason behind it was if the awakener could be caught, he should be put into confinement. Amal Tripathi had written that Government became tensed after the release of Aurobindo from jail. He had a pernicious influence as he was the pivot of the revolutionary movements. He had greater role than any other Indians in encouraging revolt against the rulers.

Aurobindo had contemplated that the Government's attitude would undergo a change and be softened after the publication of the Open Letter. But he soon understood that Government's conviction about him had remained the same. Accordingly, Aurobindo wrote another Open Letter in *Karmayogin* on 25th December in a subdued tone. But the Government considered a part of the letter as seditious. Nivedita apprehended that the Government would use this as a plea for arresting Aurobindo. She sent this open letter to her friends in the west and endeavoured to create a strong public support for him. She urged Mr. Ratcliffe to publish the letter in different dailies in England so that people could figure out that the letter in no way was anti British in fervour. Ratcliffe kept his words and the news was published in *Daily Mail* and *Times* where the British Government was criticized. Even Ramsay Macdonald questioned in the British Parliament why the order for Aurobindo's detention had been issued. Nivedita informed him that the Government had dropped the plan of his incarceration. Although a political extremist and extremely hostile towards the British rule, Nivedita had friendly relations with many higher officials of the Government. Probably the police suspected her because of her intimate relation with Aurobindo.

On 24th January, 1910, Shamsual Alam, the Deputy Superintendent of the Detective Department who was in charge of Alipore bomb cases was murdered in the court. Aurobindo's certain write ups after this incident agitated the Government. He had written in the *Karmayogin*, "the victim was the right hand man of Mr. Norton in Alipore bomb case." On 26th January, this act of the terrorists was appreciated as the 'boldest of the many bold acts of violence'. As Girija Shankar Roychoudhury had mentioned that Aurobindo was informed before the assassination and he had given his consent. The Government and the higher officials were of the firm conviction that he was the main instigator behind the murder. Amal Tripathi had mentioned that Aurobindo always gave instructions from within and signed the instructions as "Kali". After the incident, Government desperately supported Aurobindo's capture. The lieutenant Governor Becker had stated about Aurobindo that he was "not a mere blind, unreasoning tool, but an active generator of revolutionary sentiment." (Sengupta, 2014). He had written to Lord Minto, "to release Aurobindo is to ensure recrudescence at any time of further spread of evil. " Nivedita became anxious about Aurobindo's arrest. She informed him the news and Aurobindo left Calcutta. He later remarked that he had moved out not because of Nivedita's warning but he had received instruction from above.

Aurobindo's Departure to Chandannagore and stories related to it:

In February, 1910, Sri Aurobindo left for Chandannagore. The date of his shift to Chandannagore is not exactly known but Nivedita visited Chandannagore on 14th and 28th February. Many legends had been circulated regarding Aurobindo's going away to

Chandannagore. Ramachandra Majumder, a close associate of Aurobindo gave the news of Aurobindo's arrest. Nivedita advised him to hide. He accepted her words and met Nivedita at her residence in Bosepara Lane before going to the Ganges ghat for sailing towards Chandannagore. Another anecdote was that Yogin Ma first heard the news of Aurobindo's detention and Brahmachari Ganen carried this news to Aurobindo. Lizelle Reymond had mentioned that Aurobindo met Shree Ma at her *Udbodhyon* house and then the Sister and Ganen Maharaj accompanied Aurobindo to the Ghat. As stated by Aurobindo, Ramachandra Majumder gave him the information that the *Karmayogin* office would be searched and he would be confined. Aurobindo received divine instruction very soon that he must move towards Chandannagore. He reached the ghat within ten minutes and started for Chandannagore in a boat. So, he did not have time to meet Nivedita. He had sent one of his men to give the message of his departure to Nivedita and request her to take the charge of the publication of *Karmayogin* in his absence. Nivedita accepted it and took the charge of the paper as long as it was published. Aurobindo denied that he did not shift to Chandannagore on Nivedita's recommendation but his leaving of British India was divinely ordained. Most likely Nivedita did not meet Aurobindo before his exodus, because of which she hurriedly moved to Chandannagore on 14th February, 1910 although it was a day of Saraswati puja and a day of big celebration in her school. She again visited Chandannagore on 28th February. She had no other reasons for going to Chandannagore for two days except that of meeting Aurobindo as she was always worried about him. It is heard that she had arranged the passage money of Aurobindo's journey to Pondicherry from Sri Jagadish Chandra Bose.

It has also been opined that Nivedita became overtired and depressed after Aurobindo's exit. This statement is false as she was not a lady of feeble nature. She did not join politics or engage in the service of the nation depending on Aurobindo. She entered the freedom struggle much before her meeting with Aurobindo. She had not even wasted time in mourning after the demise of her Guru and busied herself with her service to the nation. She had always wished that the national movement be successful and India be free from foreign yoke. She madly loved India. She had selflessly lent a hand to Aurobindo and had taken the charge of the newspaper. This was her nature i.e to extend her support and cooperation, inspire and dedicate herself boldly for a cause. She had been only stirred by her Guru. She was steady in her ideals and unsullied in her talents. She took the charge of *Karmayogin* from February to 2nd April, 1910 when it was finally closed. Under her able guidance, the articles that were published mainly spoke of Swami Vivekananda's principles and words. In one of its issues, Nivedita had mentioned that she believed that India was one, united and undivided entity. The present was linked to the past and a bright future waited for India. Okakura had rightly remarked, 'Vivekananda is dead but He has left His spiritual daughter to lead you.' (Roychoudhury, 1960).

Aurobindo later had denied Nivedita's contributions. He had voiced that she was the leading revolutionary leader. His cooperation with her was solely in the revolutionary actions. They both were engaged in their work. So, there was no time to consult with her or take combined decisions in leading the revolutionary movement. But this was well known at that time that there was a deep revolutionary connection between them. She had given him the information

of his arrest in advance and had arranged for his disappearance to French occupied Chandannagore. This is well established from the words of Aurobindo's intimate associates. She had taken the charge of *Karmayogin* and had written the editorials so that Government would not realize his absence. It is difficult to speculate why Aurobindo had maintained confidentiality about his relation with her. Both had learnt that revolutionary work should be kept behind the veil. Nivedita also did not mention his name to her close relations in her letters. They would not mention the names of politically dangerous persons in their letters (Kolkata Puroshree, 2018). Although not in the forefront but she had always been a silent, selfless worker behind the scene.

Results:

India's freedom struggle had been the story of many nationalists, patriots, leaders, revolutionaries and foreigners who had played a very vital character in the country's political emancipation from the British rule. We are indebted to them for our freedom and life. Sister Nivedita and Sri Aurobindo were two great personalities without whom the history of the nationalist movement would remain untold. They both were western educated, sophisticated, had closely seen the occident and could have lived a luxurious life. But both shunned the lavishness of material life and dedicated themselves for the land with the difference that Sister Nivedita had adopted the country as her own and became Indian in heart and soul, where as Aurobindo was the son of the soil who loved this soil not as an object but worshipped her as the Mother. Thus, the two great nationalists had their own role to play in the nationalist movement. There were similarities as well as dissimilarities in the thoughts and deeds of Nivedita and Sri Aurobindo. Irrespective of the differences, they had a deep mutual reverence for one another and they were good allies working and selflessly dedicating themselves for the country. India owes a lot to these two pre-eminent personalities for their contributions in achieving India's independence. Nivedita had been the mother, friend and mistress of India where as Aurobindo was a politician in the garb of spiritual icon.s

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